

Tuning biphasic electrolytes for membrane-free redox flow batteries: influence of sodium thiocyanate on partition and viscosity

Murilo L. Alcantara^a, Paula Navalpotro^b, Gabriel Camilo^a, Marco Prazeres^a, Catarina M.S.S. Neves^a, Ana Maria Ferreira^a, Edgar Ventosa^c, Rebeca Marcilla^b, João A.P. Coutinho^{a,*}

^a CICECO – Aveiro Institute of Materials, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^b IMDEA – Energy, Electrochemical Processes Unit, Móstoles 28935, Spain

^c ICCRAM – International Research Center in Critical Raw Materials, University of Burgos, Pza. Misael Bañuelos s/n, E-09001 Burgos, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Membrane-free redox flow batteries (RFBs) offer a promising alternative to conventional systems by removing costly and degradation-prone ion-selective membranes. However, achieving low cross-contamination of redox-active species while maintaining low viscosity remains a key challenge. This study investigates the effect of sodium thiocyanate (NaSCN) on the partitioning of methyl viologen (MV) and TEMPO, as well as on the thermophysical properties of aqueous biphasic systems (ABS) designed for membrane-free RFBs. Four ABS were studied, comprising ammonium sulfate ((NH₄)₂SO₄) and various ionic liquids (ILs): [N₄₄₄₄]Cl, [N₄₄₄₄]Br, [P₄₄₄₄]Cl, and [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl. NaSCN addition promoted anion exchange, replacing Cl⁻ and Br⁻ with SCN⁻, leading to strong segregation of IL cations and SCN⁻ in the IL-rich phase and displacement of hydrophilic ions and water to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase. This improved MV/TEMPO separation but also increased the viscosity of the IL-rich phase, especially at NaSCN concentrations above 9 wt%. At moderate concentrations (~3.5 wt%), NaSCN enhanced species partitioning while keeping IL-rich phase viscosities below 20 mPa·s (except for [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl). The IL molecular structure, particularly alkyl chain length, critically influenced both MV/TEMPO selectivities and electrolyte viscosities. COSMO-RS simulations successfully predicted phase preferences but showed deviations in partition coefficients, especially at high NaSCN levels. These results reveal a tunable trade-off between redox species separation and viscosity, driven by IL composition and NaSCN content, and offer a foundation for designing efficient, scalable electrolytes for membrane-free RFB applications.

1. Introduction

The growing demand for sustainable energy solutions has driven the progress in solar and wind power generation [1]. However, the intermittent nature of these sources necessitates efficient energy storage systems (ESSs) to ensure grid stability and reliability [2]. Among the diverse storage technologies, redox flow batteries (RFBs) have emerged as a promising large-scale solution due to their ability to decouple power from energy density, enabling flexible and scalable operation [3,4]. This key characteristic arises from the distinct configuration of RFBs, where energy storage is determined by the concentration of active species dissolved in the externally stored liquid electrolytes, while power is governed by the size of the reactor. Despite these advantages, conventional RFBs face significant challenges, including low energy density,

sustainability concerns, and high cost [5,6]. Notably, existing commercial flow batteries (all-V, Zn–Br) are still far beyond feasibility targets (DoE = USD\$ 100 kWh⁻¹), requiring alternative systems and further improvements for effective market penetration [6].

Currently, RFBs based on vanadium chemistry and Nafion® ion-exchange membrane dominate the market. However, their dependence on vanadium, a critical raw material along with the use of expensive and inefficient Nafion membranes limits their widespread use [3]. In response, redox-active organic molecules (ROMs) have been explored as an alternative, offering synthetic versatility, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness [7]. Nevertheless, ROM-based RFB introduce new technical challenges, including ensuring long-term chemical stability and addressing ROM crossover between electrolytes which arises from the poor performance of membranes. These challenges lead to capacity loss

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: jcoutinho@ua.pt (J.A.P. Coutinho).

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and reduced cycle life [5,6].

One promising strategy to address the high cost and performance limitations of ion-selective membranes is the development of membrane-free RFBs. These systems utilize liquid-liquid phase separation to confine redox-active species, eliminating the need for a physical barrier [8]. This approach aligns with thermodynamic principles by leveraging immiscible electrolyte phases to reduce active species crossover while maintaining high ion mobility [9]. While proof-of-concept studies have demonstrated promising results, achieving consistent phase stability, optimal partitioning of active species, and controlled viscosity remains a challenge [10].

One proposed strategy to deal with the limitations of ion-selective membranes is the development of membrane-free RFBs, which rely on liquid-liquid phase separation to confine redox-active species instead of using a physical barrier [8]. This approach aligns with thermodynamic principles by leveraging immiscible electrolyte phases to reduce ion crossover while maintaining high ion mobility [9]. While proof-of-concept studies have demonstrated promising results, achieving consistent phase stability, optimal species partitioning, and controlled viscosity remains a challenge [10].

Aqueous biphasic systems (ABS) provide a promising platform for tuning electrolyte properties while keeping high ionic conductivity, which is particularly interesting for membrane-free battery applications [11]. Ionic liquid (IL)-based ABS offers additional tunability due to their highly customizable cation-anion interactions, enabling precise control over phase behavior and the distribution of active species. However, these benefits can introduce complex trade-offs, particularly in relation to viscosity, phase stability, and overall electrochemical performance. Although other parameters such as density, water content, and phase composition are also relevant, this work focuses primarily on the partitioning efficiency of active species and viscosity as the most critical trade-off for membrane-free applications. The remaining properties were monitored qualitatively and followed expected trends, but were not analyzed in detail to maintain scope.

ILs are inherently more viscous than conventional electrolytes, which can hinder mass transport, slow reaction kinetics, and increase energy losses due to elevated pumping requirements [12]. High viscosity is associated with reduced ion diffusivity and lower mass-transfer coefficients, directly affecting energy efficiency and system scalability [13]. Although dilution in aqueous solutions can moderate viscosity, careful selection and optimization of ILs and additives are essential to balance phase separation and desirable transport properties.

Additives, such as sodium thiocyanate (NaSCN), play a pivotal role in modulating ABS properties, offering a versatile approach to control phase behavior. NaSCN can enhance ionic conductivity by increasing Na^+ concentration, while SCN^- anion act as a salting-in agent, which can improve the solubility of ROMs, potentially enhancing the theoretical energy densities. However, its effect on viscosity, phase stability, and mass transport must be thoroughly evaluated to determine its viability as a tuning agent in biphasic electrolyte systems.

This study presents a systematic investigation of the thermodynamic behavior of IL-based ABS under the influence of NaSCN, focusing on phase equilibrium, species partitioning, and thermophysical properties. By understanding how IL's molecular structure and NaSCN additive concentration influence phase separation, this research provides key insights towards the rational design of tunable ABS formulations, paving the way for optimized formulations in membrane-free battery applications and beyond. Electrochemical validation in flow cells (cycling and crossover under bias) is beyond the present scope and will be addressed in subsequent work guided by these thermodynamic findings.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Supplier and purity

All materials used to form the ABS, as well as MV and TEMPO, are presented in Table 1 with their respective abbreviations. All the compounds were used as received, and no further purification was performed.

2.2. Aqueous biphasic systems

The liquid-liquid phase diagrams, also known as binodal charts, were determined gravimetrically ($\pm 10^{-4}$ g) using the cloud-point titration method at room temperature (298 ± 1 K) and atmospheric pressure, following established procedures [14,15]. Briefly, a salt-aqueous solution (~ 40 wt%) was added dropwise into a homogeneous IL solution (~ 80 wt%) under constant stirring until the system became cloudy, indicating phase separation (biphasic region). Subsequently, water was added dropwise until the system returned to the monophasic (clear) state. This titration process was repeated until no further phase change was observed. The mass of each added component was recorded before and after addition, enabling a mass balance analysis to determine multiple points along the phase transition curve.

NaSCN was incorporated into the ABS using two approaches to ensure phase stability and avoid solid precipitation. In the first approach, water was replaced with a NaSCN-concentrated solution, to avoid precipitation within the biphasic region. To determine the appropriate concentration, a mixture point near the binodal curve was selected, where pure water was substituted by a NaSCN aqueous solution. To ensure phase stability, the initial NaSCN concentration was defined as the highest value tolerated by all ABS without triggering precipitation. Although this method may appear more complex, it allows for precise control over composition while minimizing the risk of precipitation. Additionally, using a pre-dissolved NaSCN solution accelerates ABS preparation and ensures homogeneity. For example, in a mixture containing 30 wt% IL, 15 wt% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, and 55 wt% pure water, replacing the water with 55 wt% of a 1 M NaSCN solution results in a final composition of 30.0 wt% IL, 15 wt% $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 50.5 wt% pure water, and 4.5 wt% NaSCN.

In the second approach, higher NaSCN concentrations were investigated. To prevent solid precipitation, the proportions of IL and/or $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ were adjusted to accommodate the increased NaSCN content. This strategy aimed to evaluate the impact of elevated NaSCN concentrations on phase stability and species selectivity within the ABS.

2.3. Ion chromatography (IC)

The concentrations of NH_4^+ , Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} , SCN^- , Cl^- , and Br^- were quantified by triplicate using ion chromatography (IC) using a 930 Compact IC Flex chromatographer. The method was validated by comparing SCN^- partition estimated from IC and UV-vis measurements.

Table 1

Name, acronym, purity and supplier of the ionic liquids, inorganic salts and redox species used in this work.

Name	Acronym	Purity	Supplier
Tetrabutylphosphonium chloride	[P ₄₄₄₄]Cl	95 %	Iolitec
Tributyltetradecylphosphonium chloride	[P ₄₄₄₁₄]Cl	95 %	Iolitec
Tetrabutylammonium chloride	[N ₄₄₄₄]Cl	97 %	Sigma
Tetrabutylammonium bromide	[N ₄₄₄₄]Br	98 %	Sigma
Methyl Viologen Dichloride Hydrate	MV	98 %	Sigma
2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl radical	TEMPO	98 %	Sigma
Ammonium sulfate	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	99.5 %	Panreac
Sodium thiocyanate	NaSCN	98 %	Merck
Solution (Iron(III) nitrate nonahydrate)	$\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	98 %	Alfa Aesar
Nitric acid	HNO_3	65 %	Fluka

Although IL cations $[P_{4444}]^+$, $[P_{44414}]^+$ and $[N_{4444}]^+$ were measured by IC, their concentrations were estimated via charge balance on each phase (Supplementary Material section 2). Water content was estimated via mass balance. This approach was validated by comparing water content estimations with Karl Fischer measurements.

2.4. Validation via SCN^- quantification

The partition coefficient of SCN^- were measured by UV-vis for the purpose of validating IC measurements. The selection of SCN^- ion was due to its importance on the present study, as part of NaSCN. Partition coefficients were quantified by their concentrations on top and bottom phases (see Eq. 1). The concentrations quantified via a spectroscopic methodology was employed, following the procedure adapted from Hovinen et al. [16]. UV-vis absorption was measured on a Microplate reader (Synergy^{HT}), and calibration curve was prepared using a 0.200 M $Fe(NO_3)_3$ in 1 M HNO_3 and a 2.00×10^{-4} M NaSCN solution in water.

To determine the concentration of SCN^- in each phase of the system, To determine the molar absorption coefficient of the $FeSCN^{2+}$ complex, twelve solutions were prepared in test tubes by mixing different concentrations of the $Fe(NO_3)_3$ and NaSCN solutions. The absorbance of SCN^- of each sample was acquired by reducing the absorbance of a blank solution, containing only $Fe(NO_3)_3$ and water under equivalent concentrations. The $FeSCN^{2+}$ concentration in each solution was calculated based on the assumption that, under conditions where $[Fe]^{3+} \gg [SCN^-]$, all SCN^- ions quantitatively reacted to form $FeSCN^{2+}$ complexes. The absorbance was then plotted as a function of $FeSCN^{2+}$ concentration.

To determine SCN^- in the different phases, samples from both phases were collected and diluted at a ratio between 100:1 and 200:1. Then, 0.02 g of the diluted sample was mixed with 2 g of the iron nitrate solution. The systems were analyzed in triplicate (additional information available in the Supplementary Material).

2.5. Water content, phases mass and pH

Water content was determined using Karl Fischer (KF) titration to quantify the amount of water in each phase accurately. Measurements were conducted using an automatic Karl Fischer titrator (Eco KF Titrator, Metrohm, Switzerland) with Hydranal Composite 5 reagent. Prior to ABS preparation, the water content of all species involved was measured to ensure accurate water concentration corrections at the mixture point and for mass balance validation.

After reaching equilibrium, the ABS phases were separated, and the bottom phase was collected and weighed. These values were used to assess water migration upon NaSCN addition and to perform charge & mass balances.

The pH is of great importance for electrochemical cell applications. The pH of the coexisting phases in 6 ABS under study was measured using a pH meter (Metrohm, 914 model, Switzerland). The pH meter was calibrated prior to measurements using two standard buffer solutions (pH 7.00 and 4.00 ± 0.02) to ensure accuracy. Measurements were conducted at 298.15 ± 0.02 K, with each sample analyzed in triplicate to account for variability.

2.6. Density and viscosity

Measurements of viscosity and density of the top phase were carried out between 293.15 K and 308.15 K, with 5 K steps, at atmospheric pressure using a Stabinger viscometer-densimeter (Anton Paar, model SVM 3000). The temperature uncertainty was ± 0.02 K within the evaluated range. The relative uncertainty of the dynamic viscosity was ± 0.5 %, and the absolute uncertainty of the density was ± 0.0005 g·cm⁻³. Uncertainties were determined based on the manufacturer's specifications.

2.7. Partition coefficients of redox-active species

A UV-Vis microplate reader (BioTek, Synergy HT) was used to quantify the partitioning of the redox-active species MV, TEMPO, and $FeSCN^{2+}$. Optimal absorption wavelengths were selected to minimize spectral overlap and interference, with 257 nm for TEMPO, 240 nm for MV, and 447 nm for $FeSCN^{2+}$.

To ensure complete phase separation, ABS samples containing the electroactive compounds were prepared within the biphasic region and allowed to equilibrate overnight at ambient temperature and pressure. After equilibrium, the top and bottom phases were carefully separated and analyzed by UV-Vis spectrophotometry. The partition coefficient (K) were calculated according to Eq. 1. Additional information can be found within the supplementary material section 1.

$$K = \frac{[target\ compound]_{top}}{[target\ compound]_{bottom}} \quad (1)$$

2.8. Conductor-like screening model for real solvents (COSMO-RS)

The COSMO-RS model [17–19] was utilized in this study to predict the partition coefficients of MV and TEMPO across the investigated aqueous biphasic systems. This model is particularly valuable as it enables the estimation of interaction energies between system components, facilitates the prediction of behavior in experimentally untested systems, and supports efficient screening of potential materials. These capabilities are essential for optimizing biphasic electrolytes in membrane-free RFBs, as they offer deeper insight into molecular interactions, support the design of solute and solvent formulations, and accelerate the development of high-performance systems.

In the COSMO-RS calculations, all ions were treated as separate species during charge density computations, with the exception of MV, which was modeled using an ion-pair approach. This method was adopted based on prior studies indicating improved accuracy for this redox-active organic molecule [20]. To enhance the precision of the predictions, experimentally determined ion concentrations — obtained via ion chromatography (IC) — were incorporated into the model to accurately represent the compositions of the ABS phases. This approach has been demonstrated to increase accuracy in predicting partition coefficients for aqueous-organic biphasic systems [21].

Molecular geometries and charge densities were optimized using density functional theory (DFT) with the BP86 functional and the def2-TZVPD basis set, employing the TURBOMOLE software package [22] via the TMoleX v.4.5 interface [23]. The 'FINE' approach was used for constructing molecular surface cavities, corresponding to the 'BP-TZVPD-FINE_25' parametrization [24] in COSMOTerm v.25 [25]. This parametrization is recognized for its superior predictive quality in ionic systems, as it incorporates advanced corrections for hydrogen bonding, van der Waals dispersion, and residual dielectric charge [26,27]. The application of COSMO-RS in this work serves as a powerful tool for guiding the design and refinement of ABS formulations for energy storage applications.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Aqueous biphasic systems

The aqueous biphasic systems under study were formulated with water, $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ as the salting-out agent, and an ionic liquid. In selected systems, varying concentrations of sodium thiocyanate (NaSCN) were introduced to assess its impact on species partitioning and overall ABS properties.

Previous studies have shown that IL- or polymer-based ABS formed with ammonium sulfate $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ present a wide liquid-liquid biphasic region, with a low risk of solid-phase formation under typical operating conditions [11]. Furthermore, this salt was reported to produce ABS

with high selectivity in directing ROMs with positive and negative redox potentials into distinct phases, an attribute considered highly advantageous for membrane-free RFB applications [6,7,28]. Based on these favorable characteristics, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ was selected as the main salt to promote salting out and ABS formation within this study.

Quaternary phosphonium and ammonium ILs were selected for this study as they have been widely studied as phase-forming agents in ABS due to their ability to induce liquid-liquid immiscibility and modulate electrolyte properties [11]. To systematically evaluate the impact of alkyl chain length on phase behavior and ROM partitioning, two quaternary phosphonium ILs were selected: tributyltetradecylphosphonium chloride ($[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$) and tetrabutylphosphonium chloride ($[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$). The selection of $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$ was based on its proven ability to facilitate MV partitioning [28], making it a suitable benchmark for comparing partitioning behavior and studying its density and viscosity. In contrast, $[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, with a shorter alkyl chain, was selected to investigate whether reduced hydrophobic interactions could modulate redox mediator partitioning and affect the viscosity of ABS phases.

A similar approach was applied to the selection of quaternary ammonium ILs, chosen to evaluate the role of counterions in ABS phase stability, ionic interactions, and ROM distribution. Two ILs with identical alkyl chains but different anions were considered: tetrabutylammonium chloride ($[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$) and tetrabutylammonium bromide ($[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$). The selection of chloride (Cl^-) and bromide (Br^-) counterions was based on their distinct hydration properties, phase separation tendencies, and ability to influence redox mediator selectivity and ion partition, particularly for $[\text{SCN}]^-$. Studies indicate that Cl^- forms stronger hydrogen bond networks with water molecules, promoting more stable biphasic formation and greater ionic strength, whereas Br^- exhibits weaker hydration effects, potentially altering ROM distribution and charge transport efficiency [29,30]. These differences are expected to impact ABS phase separation, ROM selective partitioning, and viscosity. Furthermore, insights from IL-ABS systems demonstrate that fine-tuning IL composition can lead to enhanced phase selectivity of active species while maintaining low viscosity, crucial for efficient energy storage applications [11].

Preliminary evaluations [31,32] and exploratory analyses [33] indicate that methyl viologen (MV) and 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (TEMPO) are among the most promising organic redox active materials for membrane-free flow batteries. Previous research has shown that, in various ABS composed of ionic liquids and sulfate salts, TEMPO preferentially partitions into the IL-rich phase [28]. In contrast, viologen derivatives exhibit more variable partitioning behavior, but the incorporation of specific functional groups can be employed to favor their partition towards the salt-rich bottom phase [28]. This selective partitioning enables the separation of MV and TEMPO into opposite phases of the ABS, allowing their use in IL-based ABS for membrane-free flow battery applications.

3.1.1. Determination of binodal curves

Fig. 1 presents the binodal liquid-liquid equilibrium curves of the ABS under study, both with and without NaSCN addition (Table S3-S8 in the Supplementary Material). These graphs illustrate the phase boundaries of the systems under study. Systems with large regions above the binodal curves are particularly relevant for membrane-free RFB applications, as they are indicative of a broad range of compositions capable of forming ABS, thereby enhancing system design flexibility.

In the absence of NaSCN (empty markers in Fig. 1), $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$ formed ABS with broader biphasic regions than $[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, particularly at lower $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentrations.

3.1.2. Effect of NaSCN addition

To introduce NaSCN, pure water was replaced with NaSCN aqueous solutions at varying concentrations, ensuring phase stability while minimizing solid precipitation risks. Solutions at 2.0 M and 1.5 M NaSCN led to solid precipitation across all ABS formulations. In contrast,

Fig. 1. Binodal curves of aqueous systems formed with the studied ILs, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, with 1 M solution of NaSCN (filled markers) or without NaSCN addition (empty markers).

1.25 M NaSCN yielded solid-free ABS for $[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$, while $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$ required a lower concentration (1.0 M NaSCN) to avoid precipitation. These findings suggest an upper limit of NaSCN solubility at a fixed IL/ $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ mass ratio of 30/15, corresponding to ~ 5.5 to ~ 6.5 wt% NaSCN for $[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$ -based ABS, and ~ 5.5 to ~ 4.5 wt% for $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$.

The binodal curves obtained with 1 M NaSCN aqueous solutions (filled markers in Fig. 1) revealed that ABS formed with $[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$ approached near-complete phase separation. In the case of $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$, the liquid-liquid regions were so wide and close to the graph axis that the quantifications of their binodal points were compromised. A comparison between ABS formulated without NaSCN and those incorporating 1 M NaSCN shows that the addition of NaSCN significantly expands the biphasic region, which is particularly advantageous for membrane-free RFB applications. This allows a broader range of compositions to be explored, offering greater flexibility in optimizing key system properties such as partitioning behavior, viscosity, density, and phase volume ratios. This tunability is critical for tailoring ABS performance to meet the specific demands of energy storage systems.

3.1.3. Mixture points

Nineteen mixture points (MPs) were selected for this study. Table 2 presents the compositions of these mixtures and the nomenclature used to reference these systems throughout the study. Four of these mixture points (MPs 1, 6, 11, and 16) did not contain NaSCN, serving as reference systems for each ionic liquid (IL). These points were chosen for their proximity to the binodal curve, representing formulations with the minimum amounts of salt and IL required to form an aqueous biphasic system (ABS).

Twelve mixture points (MPs 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, and 19) were prepared using a 1 M NaSCN aqueous solution instead of pure water. These ABS contained approximately 3.5 wt% NaSCN, which was determined to be a suitable concentration for producing ABS with all ILs without causing solid precipitation. Three mixture points for each ABS were selected to evaluate the effects of small variations in IL and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ concentrations on species partitioning and thermophysical properties.

Additionally, three ABS (MPs 5, 10, and 15) were prepared with at least double the NaSCN content to assess its impact on ABS properties. To achieve NaSCN concentrations ranging from 9 to 13 wt%, the IL concentration was partially reduced to prevent solid precipitation. Notably, no mixture point with higher NaSCN concentration was prepared for ABS formed with $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$, as it was not possible to produce an ABS without solid precipitation at NaSCN concentrations above

Table 2
19 mixture points of the 4 ABS under study.

MP	ABS (% wt.)	NaSCN (%wt.)	IL (% wt.)	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (wt.)	H ₂ O ^a (wt.)	1 M sol ^b (% wt.)
1	0 % NaSCN; 25 % [P ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 17 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	0.0	24.4	16.6	59.0	–
2	+40 % [P ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 15 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	3.2	39.1	15.0	42.7	44.0
3	+30 % [P ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 20 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	3.6	29.3	20.0	47.0	50.0
4	+40 % [P ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 20 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	2.9	39.0	20.0	38.1	40.0
5	9 % NaSCN + 15 % [P ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 16 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	8.5	15.2	15.9	60.1	–
6	0 % NaSCN; 31 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 12 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	0.0	31.2	11.5	57.3	–
7	+40 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 15 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	2.9	38.6	15.0	43.5	40.0
8	+30 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 15 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	4.0	28.9	15.0	52.0	55.0
9	+40 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 10 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 13 % NaSCN	3.6	38.6	10.1	47.7	50.0
10	+20 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Cl + 10 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	12.8	19.6	10.0	57.3	–
11	0 % NaSCN; 32 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Br + 10 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	0.0	31.4	9.8	58.8	–
12	+30 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Br + 15 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	4.0	29.8	15.0	51.1	55.0
13	+40 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Br + 10 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	3.6	39.8	10.0	46.5	50.0
14	+40 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Br + 15 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 11 % NaSCN	3.3	39.8	15.0	41.9	45.0
15	+21 % [N ₄₄₄₄]Br + 10 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	10.7	20.7	9.9	58.4	–
16	0 % NaSCN; 30 % [P ₄₄₄₁₄]Cl + 10 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	0.0	30.3	9.6	60.0	–
17	+40 % [P ₄₄₄₁₄]Cl + 20 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	2.9	38.5	20.0	38.6	40.0
18	+30 % [P ₄₄₄₁₄]Cl + 20 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ 3.5 % NaSCN	3.6	28.9	20.0	47.5	50.0
19	+40 % [P ₄₄₄₁₄]Cl + 15 % (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	3.3	38.5	15.0	43.2	45.0

^a mass concentration of pure water.

^b mass concentration of aqueous solution added to form the ABS instead of pure water.

approximately 4 wt%, which is similar to those prepared with the 1 M NaSCN aqueous solution.

3.2. Partition behavior of ions

This section explores the partition of all ions on IL-rich and bottom phases of the 4 studied ABS. IC measurements of ions concentrations were validated by comparison of SCN[−] partition with UV–vis method (Supplementary Material, Fig. S4). The estimations of ILs' cations concentrations were validated by performing a mass balance and comparing the total mass concentrations of ions in the ABS, estimated from ILs' cations estimations and weighted amount of salts added to form the ABS (Supplementary Material, Table S17).

Fig. 2 presents ion partitioning behavior across all 19 studied ABS. NaSCN-free ABS present overall similar ion partition behavior, with preferential partition of ILs' ions [P₄₄₄₄]⁺, [N₄₄₄₄]⁺, [P₄₄₄₁₄]⁺, Cl[−] and Br[−], to the IL-rich phase (so called IL/"Organic"-rich), while the ions of the salt, NH₄⁺ and SO₄^{2−}, preferentially partition to the bottom phase (so called salt/(NH₄)₂SO₄-rich). This behavior is consistent with previous findings, which suggest that quaternary ammonium and phosphonium ILs tend to preferentially partition into the more hydrophobic phase of an ABS due to their charge distribution and solvation properties [11].

By comparing the partition of ions in ABS formed with [N₄₄₄₄]Cl and [N₄₄₄₄]Br, it is possible to observe a small yet clear difference in the behavior of Br[−] and Cl[−] ions' effects. On NaSCN-free ABS (MP 1, 6 11 and 16), Br[−] ions remain less concentrated in the bottom phase (salt-rich) compared to Cl[−]. This difference can be attributed to the bromide anion exhibiting a more delocalized charge distribution and weaker hydration effects compared to chloride anions; therefore, leading to weaker ion-water interactions [30,34]. As a result, [N₄₄₄₄]Br experiences stronger salting-out effects from the SO₄^{2−} rich bottom phase, favoring its partition into the IL-rich phase, where hydrophobic interactions dominate (Fig. 2). Although chlorine anion also preferentially partition to the IL-rich phase, however, their higher charge density and more strongly hydrated shell maintains a higher affinity with water than Br[−], and for that reason they can be found in a higher concentration on the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase (Fig. 2). Presumably, Cl[−] can promote higher contribution to phase stabilization through stronger electrostatic interactions [29].

When NaSCN is added as a 1 M solution (equivalent to adding about ~3.5 wt% of NaSCN in the whole ABS), a nearly complete ion exchange occurs (entries 2–4, 7–9, 12–14, and 17–19). This is confirmed by the nearly complete partition of SCN[−] anions (blue bars) to the IL-rich phase, reaching partition coefficients ranging from 100 to 1000 (Log K = 2 to 3). Additionally, it can also be observed a decrease in the partition coefficient of Cl[−]/Br[−] (red bars), approaching 1 (Log K = 0) or below. The SCN[−] anions preferentially interact with the IL cations [N₄₄₄₄]⁺, [P₄₄₄₄]⁺ and [P₄₄₄₁₄]⁺, displacing their original counterions (Cl[−] and Br[−], red bars) to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase, where they charge compensate for Na⁺ cations from NaSCN (i.e., anion exchange occurs). The small partition of ILs' original counter anions, Cl[−] and Br[−], indicate that the ion exchange was incomplete at 1 M NaSCN, so a fraction of the IL's original anion remains in the IL-rich phase (~3.5 wt%). Thus, part of the original IL can still be found within the IL-rich phase. The higher affinity of SCN[−] for IL-rich phase further confirms the more favorable interactions between this anion and ILs' cations [N₄₄₄₄]⁺, [P₄₄₄₄]⁺ and [P₄₄₄₁₄]⁺, which are likely influenced by the different hydration properties of Br[−] and Cl[−] in the absence of NaSCN.

At higher NaSCN concentrations (9–13 wt%, MP 5, 10 and 15) ion exchange in the IL-rich phase became nearly complete. This is evidenced by the IL cations (dashed bars) remaining almost exclusively in the top phase, while their original counterions, Cl[−] and Br[−], preferentially migrated to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase. Additionally, part of the SCN[−]

Fig. 2. Partition coefficient of ions in all 19 mixture points of 4 ABS under study.

that exceeded IL's anion exchange migrated to the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase, which reduced SCN^- partition coefficient to the IL-rich phase. All partition coefficients as well as concentrations in mol and mass percentage can be verified in the supplementary material, Tables S12 to S59.

3.3. Water content, phases mass and pH

Fig. 3 presents the water content ($\% g_{\text{water}}/g_{\text{solution}}$, shown as empty bars) and the mass ratio of the IL-rich and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phases ($\%$

Fig. 3. Water content (filled bars) and mass ratio (empty bars) of IL-rich (blue) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich (red) phases of all ABS under study. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

m_i/m_{total} , shown as filled bars) for all ABS under study. To facilitate visualization, the values corresponding to the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase were multiplied by (-1) , ensuring their identification in the negative quadrants of the graph (bottom).

The results demonstrate that the addition of NaSCN leads to a reduction in the mass ratio of IL-rich phase, with this decrease being more pronounced at higher NaSCN concentration (entries 5, 10, and 15 in Table 1 and Fig. 2). The water content of IL-rich phase also decreases significantly, while it increases in the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase. This behavior clearly indicates that the NaSCN addition promotes the migration of water from the IL-rich to the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase in all ABS under study. This phenomenon is attributed to the anion exchange of Cl^- by SCN^- in the IL-rich phase, along with the migration of most hydrophilic ions (NH_4^+ , Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^-/Br^-) towards the bottom phase, as evidenced by the ion profiles shown on Fig. 2. It is important to note that this does not imply SCN^- itself is hydrophobic; rather, its weaker hydration compared to Cl^-/Br^- modifies the ion distribution and drives the observed water transfer. As discussed, the ion and water migration induced by the addition of NaSCN leads to significant changes in the composition of both the IL-rich and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phases, and is expected to also affect other key parameters such as density and viscosity.

3.4. Density

The densities of both phases were analyzed for six systems composed of $[\text{P}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Cl}$, and $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$. Three of them without NaSCN (entries 1, 6 and 11 in Table 1), and three with varying concentrations of NaSCN (entries 5, 10, and 15 in Table 1). The density differences between the top (Fig. 4b, blue) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich (Fig. 4a, red) phases ranged from 0.08 to 0.22 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. Addition of NaSCN salt significantly reduced the density of the IL-rich phases (Fig. 4b), whose values converged around 0.96 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. Regarding the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phases (Fig. 4a), the addition of NaSCN led to a reduction in density, except for the system based on $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$ (red triangles), which exhibited an opposite trend, with density increasing as NaSCN concentration increased. This highlights the significant role of the IL anion in modulating phase composition and density.

Overall, the addition of NaSCN enhances the density difference between phases, particularly in ABS based on $[\text{N}_{4444}]\text{Br}$. It is important to highlight that enhanced density difference facilitates more efficient phase separation, which is especially beneficial under the flow conditions encountered in membrane-free redox flow batteries, where minimizing interphase mixing is critical to maintaining high operational efficiency.

Fig. 4. Density of IL-rich (a, blue) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich (b, red) phases of ABS prepared without NaSCN (empty symbols; entries 1, 6 and 11 in Table 1) and with 9–13 wt% of NaSCN (filled symbols; entries 5, 10 and 15 in Table 1). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3.5. Viscosity

Ensuring low viscosity is crucial to achieve an efficient performance in RFBs, minimizing pumping energy consumption and maintaining high ion mobility. Electrolytes with viscosities below 10 mPa·s are generally considered suitable for RFB operation. [34]. Nevertheless, our previous empirical laboratory results have shown membrane-free RFB employing ABS-based electrolytes with viscosities up to 20 mPa·s can still operate effectively, with acceptable diffusion parameters and pressure drop [35]. This threshold aligns with operational RFB electrolytes, such as all-iron systems with viscosities up to 15 mPa·s for 1.5 M solutions [36] and accounts for the higher viscosities expected in IL-based aqueous biphasic systems (ABS) due to the viscous nature of ionic liquids (ILs). Thus, we adopt 20 mPa·s as a practical viscosity limit, consistent with our observations and reported ranges.

Similar to the density analysis, six aqueous biphasic systems (ABS) were selected for viscosity pre-evaluation of their IL-rich and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phases, formed with (MP: 5, 10 and 15) and without

NaSCN (entries 1, 6, and 11 in Table 1). Fig. 5 shows that the IL-rich phase consistently exhibited higher viscosities due to elevated ionic liquid (IL) concentrations (Fig. 2), which are known for their high viscosities. The addition of NaSCN reportedly induced water migration from the IL-rich to the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase (Fig. 3), resulting in a slight decrease in the bottom phase viscosities by less than 1 mPa·s. In contrast, the IL-rich phase viscosities increased significantly, by one to two orders of magnitude, when NaSCN concentrations ranged from 9 to 13 wt%. While NaSCN-free ABS exhibited IL-rich phase viscosities of 4.5 to 9.5 mPa·s, NaSCN-rich ABS reached top phase viscosities up to 131 mPa·s. ABS formed with $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$ showed higher top phase viscosities, even without NaSCN, ranging from 53 to 114 mPa·s. NaSCN concentrations of 9–13 wt% could not be evaluated in $[\text{P}_{44414}]\text{Cl}$ -based ABS due to solid precipitation above ~5 wt% NaSCN. Thus, longer alkyl chains in phosphonium ILs were found to significantly increase electrolyte viscosity and the risk of precipitation.

of ABS prepared without NaSCN at different temperatures.

The results from Fig. 5 highlight the need to define an optimal

Fig. 5. Viscosity of IL-rich (a, blue) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich (b, red) phases of ABS prepared without NaSCN (empty symbols) and with 9–13 wt% of NaSCN (filled symbols). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

NaSCN concentration that ensures both redox separation efficiency and manageable viscosity for practical use. To address this, the viscosities of the IL-rich phase in ABS prepared with lower concentrations of NaSCN were investigated, and the results are presented in Fig. 6. Three mixture points per IL-based ABS were prepared using a 1 M NaSCN solution (~3.5 wt%) instead of pure water. This intermediate NaSCN concentration yielded IL-rich phase viscosities of 4.5–68 mPa·s, except for [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl⁻ based ABS, which ranged from 85 to 245 mPa·s.

The influence of (NH₄)₂SO₄ concentration was also assessed. As shown in Fig. 6, lower concentrations of salt (represented by triangles) generally yielded IL-rich phases with lower viscosities. Moreover, the viscosity of the top phase varied depending on the IL employed, following the order: [N₄₄₄₄]Cl < [P₄₄₄₄]Cl < [N₄₄₄₄]Br < [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl. Except [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl based ABS, it was possible to find at least one mixture point for each IL that produced ABS with viscosities below the feasibility benchmark of 20 mPa·s up to 308 K (red line in Fig. 6).

In summary the viscosity of top phase electrolytes presented higher values according to the IL used, following the order: [N₄₄₄₄]Cl < [P₄₄₄₄]Cl < [N₄₄₄₄]Br < [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl. Except for the [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl, all ILs produced ABS with suitable viscosity for flow battery applications. Although no ABS prepared with 1 M NaSCN solution presented acceptable top phase viscosities for RFB operation, the addition of a moderate amount of NaSCN (about 3.5 wt%) can produce ABS with acceptable viscosities.

3.6. Partition of redox active species

Efficient partitioning of redox-active species is critical for

minimizing cross-contamination and maximizing capacity utilization in membrane-free RFBs. Since these batteries do not use any physical barrier or separator to keep the electrolytes separated, the thermodynamic selective confinement of positive and negative redox species into opposite phases ensures stable operation and high efficiency. Fig. 7 presents the partition coefficients of MV (typical active species for the anolyte) and TEMPO (typical active species for the catholyte) across the 19 mixture points of 4 ABS under study. TEMPO consistently exhibited strong partitioning towards the IL-rich phase, with partition coefficients (*K*) often exceeding 200 (Log *K* ≈ 2.3), approaching the detection limit due to concentration measurement constraints. In contrast, MV preferentially partitioned to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase, though with a lower partitioning magnitude than TEMPO to the IL-rich phase. This asymmetric partitioning effectively mitigates cross-contamination, one of the primary factors responsible for reduced capacity utilization and accelerated capacity fading during cycling. However, the relative lower partitioning of MV suggests that further enhancement of its confinement to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase is necessary to fully optimize MV/TEMPO separation and, consequently, RFB performance.

As shown in Fig. 7, phosphonium-based ILs, specifically [P₄₄₄₄]Cl and [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl, outperformed ammonium-based ILs in driving MV to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase, making them promising candidates for battery application due to low cross contamination. The ABS with 3.5 wt% NaSCN (1 M solution) presented overall enhanced MV and TEMPO partitioning compared to NaSCN free ABS and those containing more than 9 wt% of NaSCN. The [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl-based ABS prepared with 1 M NaSCN solution demonstrated the overall highest MV partitioning to the

Fig. 6. Viscosity of the top phase of ABS formed with 1 M NaSCN solution and (a) [N₄₄₄₄]Cl (entries 6–10 in Table 1), (b) [N₄₄₄₄]Br (entries 11–15 in Table 1), (c) [P₄₄₄₄]Cl (entries 1–5 in Table 1), and (d) [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl (entries 16–19 in Table 1), at three mixture points each and different temperatures, compared to a benchmark limit of 20 mPa·s represented by a red dashed line. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Partition Behavior of TEMPO and MV in 4 IL-based ABS at 19 mixture points to IL-rich (top, red) or $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich (bottom, blue) phases at different NaSCN concentrations: 0 wt% (highlighted in gray), ~ 3.5 wt%, and above 9 wt% (highlighted in red). Error bars are expanded uncertainties at 95 % confidence level ($K = 2$) and normal distribution. Conditions: 298 ± 1 K, atmospheric pressure. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase (MP 17, 18, and 19); however, two of those mixture points (17 and 18) presented a reduction on TEMPO partitioning to the IL-rich phase. The ABS prepared with 40 wt% of $[\text{P}44414]\text{Cl}$, 15 wt% of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, and 44 wt% ow 1 M solution of NaSCN (MP 19) presented the highest partition of MV and TEMPO to opposite phases, resulting in partition coefficients above 150 for each redox active species to opposite phases (Fig. 7).

Overall, ABS formed with higher salt concentration or lower IL concentrations promoted higher MV/TEMPO partition to the desired phases. While no clear trend could be found about the difference of mixture points used to form the 19 mixture points of 4 ABS, those

prepared specially with higher amount of ammonium sulfate presented overall slightly higher partition of MV to the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ -rich phase. Conversely, systems with higher salt content enhanced IL-rich phase viscosity, highlighting a trade-off between separation efficiency and fluid dynamics by changing ammonium sulfate concentration.

The combined results of viscosity and partition coefficients suggest that a concentration of NaSCN around ~ 3.5 wt% (1 M) could enhance the overall performance of these ABS to be used in RFBs. To rigorously assess the effect of NaSCN on the partitioning behavior of MV and TEMPO, measurements were conducted at identical mixture points with and without NaSCN, and the results are presented in Fig. 8. The results

Fig. 8. Comparison of TEMPO/MV partition on 12 mixture points prepared with pure water or 1 M solution of NaSCN at 298 ± 1 K and atmospheric pressure. Error bars are expanded uncertainties at 95 % confidence level ($K = 2$) and normal distribution.

show that MV partitioning increased with the addition of NaSCN in all systems, except those based on $[N_{4444}]Br$, thereby confirming the beneficial role of NaSCN in enhancing separation in chloride-based ILs. For TEMPO, partitioning showed a reduction in $[P_{44414}]Cl$ -based ABS, while one $[N_{4444}]Br$ -based system exhibited a slight increase. Globally, these findings underscore the positive effect of moderate concentration of NaSCN on the partitioning of the ROMs, supporting its potential to fine-tune membrane-free RFB performance.

The effect of the anion of the ILs (Cl^- vs. Br^-) on MV/TEMPO separation was significant from both qualitative and quantitative perspective. On NaSCN free systems, $[N_{4444}]Br$ -based ABS (MP 11–14) presented overall higher MV/TEMPO separation than $[N_{4444}]Cl$ -based ones (MP 6–9). However, the addition of NaSCN through the 1 M solution (3.5 wt%) promoted opposite effects on the two systems, by increasing MV/TEMPO separation on $[N_{4444}]Cl$ -based ABS (MP 7–9) and reducing on $[N_{4444}]Br$ (MP 12–14). NaSCN containing ABS formed with $[N_{4444}]Cl$ presented higher separation performance of the redox active species studied. This effect could be at least partially attributed to the effect of NaSCN on the concentrations of $[N_{4444}]^+$ and Cl^-/Br^- in the ABS. NaSCN-free $[N_{4444}]Br$ -based ABS systems presented much higher concentrations of $[N_{4444}]^+$ and Br^- in the top phase than $[N_{4444}]^+$ and Cl^- concentrations in $[N_{4444}]Cl$ based systems as shown in Fig. 2. Presumably, the delocalized charge of bromide and weaker hydration enhance TEMPO interactions, increasing its partition towards the IL-rich phase. However, the addition of NaSCN induced anion exchange that disrupted this behavior, modifying the phase dynamics.

Effective ABS for membrane-free RFBs must maximize MV/TEMPO separation into opposite phases while minimizing viscosity to ensure high capacity utilization, performance and operational efficiency. The $[P_{44414}]Cl$ -based ABS offers a compelling compromise, providing still suitable MV/TEMPO separation and low viscosity. The addition of a moderate amount of NaSCN (~3.5 wt% in this study) increased partitioning of MV to 63 (log $K = 1.8$) to the $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ -rich phase and TEMPO up to 200 (log $K = 2.3$) to the IL-rich phase. Therefore, increasing positive and negative ROMs partitions to opposite phases, while keeping viscosities under suitably low standards, down to 20 mPa·s benchmark at 298 K. An excessive increase in NaSCN concentration (e.g., 9–13 wt% in this study) compromises both MV/TEMPO separation performance and the viscosity of the IL-rich phase electrolyte. These findings highlight the interplay between IL structure and phase properties, guiding the design of ABS for practical membrane-free RFB applications. It is important to stress that in this work this study focus on the neutral forms of MV and TEMPO as a thermodynamic baseline to understand how NaSCN tunes partitioning and viscosity. The

behavior of their charged and discharged counterparts during battery cycling remains to be investigated and will be essential for a complete electrochemical validation. In addition, while partition coefficients in the range of 63 and 200 are already considered promising in the context of membrane-free biphasic systems, long-term cell-level tests are necessary to fully establish whether this degree of separation is sufficient to suppress self-discharge over extended operation. These results should be interpreted as baseline thermodynamic selectivity in the absence of applied bias; electrochemical validation of the charged states under operating potentials should be considered on real RFB application.

3.7. COSMO-RS

COSMO-RS was employed to estimate the partition coefficients of MV and TEMPO across the 19 ABS investigated in this study. Fig. 9 presents a comparison between the experimental and COSMO-RS-predicted partition coefficients of TEMPO and MV across all 19 ABS examined. Although the model frequently exhibits significant quantitative deviations from experimental values, it demonstrates reliable qualitative accuracy. Specifically, COSMO-RS correctly predicted the preferred phase (IL-rich or $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ -rich) for TEMPO or MV in 100 % and 84 % of the cases, respectively (Fig. 9a). Additionally, Fig. 9b highlights the model's ability to capture trends in partition behavior. Most predicted partition coefficients deviate from experimental values by up to two orders of magnitude. However, larger discrepancies are observed for ABS containing high sodium NaSCN concentrations (> 9 wt %) or those formulated with $[P_{44414}]Cl$. These pronounced deviations are likely due to the model's limitations in accurately accounting for long-range ionic interactions, which become increasingly significant in systems with elevated salt concentrations, such as those with NaSCN. Furthermore, the $[P_{44414}]Cl$ IL introduces additional challenges. Its surfactant-like properties produce complex long range interactions; moreover, its high viscosity impedes precise experimental quantification of its concentration via IC, contributing to the observed prediction errors.

In conclusion, COSMO-RS does not provide quantitatively reliable predictions of partition coefficients for the ABS under investigation. Nevertheless, it remains a valuable tool for qualitative assessments, effectively predicting phase preferences and facilitating the screening of materials for redox flow battery applications. Comparable conclusions regarding the qualitative utility of COSMO-RS have been noted in prior studies of ABS for redox flow battery systems [37].

Fig. 9. Predicted and experimental partition coefficient of MV and TEMPO on 19 studied ABS depicted via (a) bars, and (b) diagonal graph.

4. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive investigation into how IL structures and NaSCN additive influence the behavior of ABS, with a focus on ROM partitioning, water content, density, and viscosity. Binodal curves confirm that ABS formed with ammonium sulfate and quaternary ammonium and phosphonium ILs — namely [P₄₄₄₄]Cl, [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl, [N₄₄₄₄]Cl, and [N₄₄₄₄]Br — present a large biphasic region. By substituting pure water with a 1 M NaSCN solution, the biphasic region was enlarged, while maintaining a minimal risk of solid precipitation.

Ion partitioning analysis reveals a preferential migration of ILs' ions into the top phase, while ammonium sulfate ones partition to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase. The introduction of NaSCN at moderate concentrations (~3.5 wt%) induces a strong anion exchange, where SCN⁻ replaces Cl⁻ and Br⁻ in the IL-rich phase, leading to enhanced species segregation. However, at higher NaSCN concentrations (9–13 wt%), nearly complete ion exchanges are observed, and water is forced to migrate from the top to the bottom phase.

The addition of NaSCN increases density differences between the top and bottom phases, enhancing phase separation stability under dynamic flow conditions. Viscosity trends reveal a critical trade-off with NaSCN addition. All (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase viscosities remained below 2.5 mPa·s, regardless of the ionic liquid (IL) or NaSCN concentration studied. However, top phase viscosities varied widely, ranging from 4.5 to 9.5 mPa·s in NaSCN-free ABS, except for [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl-based ABS, which exceeded 50 mPa·s. NaSCN addition amplified this effect, significantly increasing top phase viscosity due to the migration of hydrophilic ions and water to the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase. NaSCN concentrations of 9–13 wt% caused substantial increases in top phase viscosities, with a minimum value of 49 mPa·s at the highest temperature evaluated. In contrast, a NaSCN concentration of approximately 3.5 wt% produced ABS with moderate top phase viscosities. At least one composition of [P₄₄₄₄]Cl, [N₄₄₄₄]Cl, and [N₄₄₄₄]Br based ABS exhibited top and bottom phase viscosities below 20 mPa·s at temperatures below 308 K, suggesting feasible mass transfer and pressure drop in redox flow batteries prepared with these materials.

While TEMPO exhibits strong partitioning into the IL-rich top phase across all studied systems, methyl viologen (MV) favors the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase. COSMO-RS was able to correctly predict this behavior in most cases; however, associated with up to two orders of magnitude of deviation of partition coefficients. Phosphonium-based ILs consistently outperform their ammonium counterparts in MV partition. The increase of alkyl chains of IL's cation, from [P₄₄₄₄]Cl to [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl, further increased MV partition to the desired phase, producing partition coefficients above 150 for MV/TEMPO on desired phases at ABS formed with 40 wt% of [P₄₄₄₁₄]Cl, 15 wt% of (NH₄)₂SO₄ and 45 wt% of 1 M solution of NaSCN. The addition of NaSCN (3.5 wt%) improved MV/TEMPO separation of chloride IL-based ABS by increasing MV's affinity for the (NH₄)₂SO₄-rich phase; however, ABS formed with bromide IL [N₄₄₄₄]Br⁻ showed an inverse trend. Increasing NaSCN concentrations beyond 9 wt% compromises separation efficiency due to reduced IL content and heightened viscosity, underscoring a critical balance between phase composition and species distribution.

The results highlight the need to optimize the IL structure and carefully select the concentration of additives such as NaSCN to tailor ABS for membrane-free redox flow battery applications. Among the systems evaluated, [P₄₄₄₄]Cl delivers the most balanced performance, achieving robust MV and TEMPO partitioning (*K* up to 63 and 200, respectively) and maintaining viscosities suitably low, reaching values below 20 mPa·s at 298 K. Overall, our findings underscore the pivotal role of IL structure and NaSCN for controlling ABS properties, offering a framework for advancing the design of electrolytes for membrane-free flow batteries.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Murilo L. Alcantara: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Paula Navalpotro:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Gabriel Camilo:** Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Marco Prazeres:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Catarina M.S.S. Neves:** Validation, Supervision. **Ana Maria Ferreira:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Edgar Ventosa:** Visualization, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Rebeca Marcilla:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis. **João A.P. Coutinho:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT 4.5 and Grok 3 in order to increase the readability and correct grammar and typo mistakes. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Ana Maria Ferreira reports financial support was provided by Foundation for Science and Technology. Murilo L. Alcantara reports financial support was provided by Foundation for Science and Technology. Gabriel Camilo reports financial support was provided by Foundation for Science and Technology. Joao Coutinho reports financial support was provided by Foundation for Science and Technology. Rebeca Marcilla reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science Technology and Innovation. Paula Navalpotro reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science and Innovation. Edgar Ventosa reports financial support was provided by European Innovation Council. Marco Prazeres reports was provided by European Innovation Council. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2025.128767>.

Data availability

I've attached the data as supplementary material attached to the submission

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